

ROLE OF ACTION RESEARCH IN THE IMPROVEMENT OF SELF AWARENESS IN TEACHING AMONG B.ED., TRAINEES.

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ABSTRACT

Teaching and Research are the two faces of the same coin. Teaching is the practical part of the Research. Teaching plays the role of education and Action Research plays the role of the Philosophy. Research in any discipline dives deep into the ocean of knowledge to discover new relations, new theories and better understanding of various phenomenons. Besides the basic role of creating of fund of knowledge, research also acts as an agent of change and improvement. Every teacher becomes a researcher to the extent that he or she perceives the problem, designs an Action Research Project, experiments to test the hypothesis and finally comes out with solution, to improve teaching and there by enhance the learning on the part of learners. As the name suggests, Action Research is the methodology which has the dual aims of action and research. In the present 2 year B.Ed., programme one of the areas of training is the school internship. One of the components is the class room based Research Project where the student trainee should undergo Action Research. This programme provides the plat form for the interns to give expression to their learning while planning and reflecting on their own experience. In present paper study on Action Research of the B.Ed., trainees are explained. The tool Self awareness in teaching was used to collect the data. Simple Statistics technique was used to analysis and interpretation of the data. The study revealed that the Action Research improved the self-awareness in teaching among the trainees.

INTRODUCTION:-

It is the one of the types of the Research, most of the times considered as methodology which has the dual aims of action and Research.

“Action research concentrate on immediate application but not in development of theory.”

Kulbir singh siddu.

The Action researches start with intention or planning before action and review or critique after. The following figure depict the Action research cycle

What out comes do i wish to Achieve?

PLAN

What action do i think will achieve the out come?

ACTION

Did i achieve the desired out comes?

Steps of the Action Research:-The steps of the Action Research are as like the Research ,But there is no any strict and rigid steps as such.

1. Identification of the problem.
2. Analysis of the problem to define and delimit it.
3. Diagnosing the factors causing the problem.
4. Formulating action hypothesis.
5. Designing the action plan
6. Collection of data and analysis/Evaluation of action hypothesis.
7. Research report writing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY.

1. To explore the improvement in teaching skill among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees
2. To explore the improvement in self-awareness in teaching among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.
3. To check the level of knowledge about the Action research among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.
4. To study the ability of analyzing and interpretation of data Through Action research among B.Ed., Teacher trainees.

5. To study the intention of application of Action research to improve their own abilities among the B.Ed., trainees.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY.

1. There is no significant improvement in teaching skill among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees through the Action Research.

2. There is no significant improvement in self awareness in teaching among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees through Action Research.

3. There is no good level of knowledge about the Action research among the B.Ed., Teacher trainees.

4. There is no ability of analyzing and interpretation of data through Action Research is developed among B.Ed.,

5. There is no intention of application of Action research to improve their own abilities among the B.Ed., trainees.

METHODOLOGY.

Method adopted. The investigator used normative survey method for collection of data.

SAMPLE.

The sample selected includes 50 2nd year B.Ed., trainees from Ballari B.Ed., colleges by using the stratified sampling technique.

TOOLS.

The investigator prepared a self awareness in teaching scale consists of 15 questions which are rated using 3point scale namely to a great extent, to some extent, not at all. Percentage analysis was done to analyze the responses of student trainees.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA.

Table 1- Responses of B.Ed., trainees on self awareness in teaching through Action Research.

SL No	Test Item	To great extent (%)	To some extent (%)	Not at all(%)
01	Action Research is very simple.	44(88)	6(12)	0(0)
02	Action Research consumes more time.	4(8)	14(28)	32(64)
03	The Researcher is the consumer in Action Research.	46(92)	4(8)	0(0)
04	Action Research develops self awareness in teaching in a teacher.	45(90)	3(6)	2(4)
05	Action Research can be taken by any professionals.	42(84)	4(8)	4(8)

06	Action Research is good for the beginners that to student teachers.	41(82)	5(10)	4(8)
07	Application of simple statistics in Action Research improves the analysis and synthesis ability in teacher trainee.	39(78)	8(16)	3(6)
08	Planning of proper educational and learning experiences is possible to teacher through the Action research plan in Action Research	45(90)	4(8)	1(2)
09	Action Research improves the teaching skills of teacher and hence the ability of understanding among learners.	47(94)	1(2)	2(4)
10	Action Research is not burden to teacher it is a part of the teaching.	33(66)	14(28)	3(6)
11	Action is the main aim of Action Research and Research is the fringe benefit of the Action.	44(88)	2(4)	4(8)
12	The aim of the Action Research is planning and execution of the proper actions not formulation of the theory.	48(96)	2(4)	0(0)
13	Outcomes of Action Research results can be extended to other teachers and generalize.	28(56)	15(30)	7(14)
14	The teacher training colleges can be document the Action Research of student trainees.	48(96)	2(4)	0(0)
15	Publication as “What research says to the class room teacher” may also publish and circulate widely.	34(68)	10(20)	6(12)

Table 1 reveals that 88% of trainees supports that Action Research is simple. But 78.5% of trainees felt that Action Research is burden and at the same time 66% trainees support that Action Research is a part of teaching. It shows that trainees are in confusion about the part of teaching and extra work. 68% trainees support the publication and wide circulation of Action Research. The statement Action is important and Research is the fringe benefit of it is accepted by 96% trainees. Action Research is develops self-awareness is supported by 90% trainees.

So the hypothesis 1 to 5 are rejected the directive Hypothesis are accepted.

Conclusion.

“Think well is wise, Planning well is wiser, Doing well is wisest” is the Persian proverb is suitable for the Action Research. It is primarily quantitative hence more responsive to situation. So strengthening the Action Research in teacher training will improve the ability of teachers and hence quality of the education. Action Research often emphasizes local relevance (that is responsive) at the cost of global relevance (that is generalization). When change is one of the intended outcomes the training colleges should adopt practice the Action Research among the trainees.

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